

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

ETHNOCULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF THE CONCEPT “HOLIDAY” IN THE LINGUISTIC WORLDVIEW (BASED ON ENGLISH, FRENCH, AND RUSSIAN)

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Abstract.

The article examines the concept of “holiday” as a key ethnocultural unit in English, French, and Russian linguistic worldviews. The study aims to identify semantic, cognitive, and cultural features of the concept through lexicographic analysis and ethnocultural interpretation. Using dictionary definitions, linguistic data, and culturally significant holidays (Christmas, La Saint-Martin, and Maslenitsa), the research reveals national-specific meanings, symbols, and values. The novelty of the work lies in the comparative cognitive analysis of the concept as realized in language, ritual, and phraseology.

Keywords: concept, holiday, linguistic worldview, ethnoculture, semantics.

Relevance. The relevance of this study is determined by the need to decode the cultural codes of different peoples through their basic concepts. The concept of “holiday” is particularly suitable for such an analysis, as it accumulates historical, religious, and ethnocultural characteristics. In an era of active intercultural dialogue, understanding how the English, French, and Russians conceptualize joyful events allows not only to reveal the ethnocultural specificity of their thinking but also to gain a deeper insight into the structure of ethnocultural linguistic worldviews.

In modern linguistics, the “concept” serves as a primary category for studying mental structures that reflect ethnocultural values. According to N. D. Arutyunova, a concept represents everyday human understanding of the world, formed from folk tales, traditions and moral notions. It functions as a “a kind of cultural layer mediating between a person and the world” [1, p. 37].

Within this framework, the concept of “*holiday*” serves as a representative unit for analyzing ethnoculturally grounded interpretations in English, French, and Russian. In cognitive linguistics, such concepts are viewed as dynamic mental structures, evolving from perceptual representations into complex formations with rational and evaluative components [9]. These structures collectively form the linguistic worldview, through which speakers process information using categories shaped by their unique historical and social context [13, p 73–76]. Ethnocultural specificity is most vividly manifested in linguistic units and fixed expressions that lack exact equivalents in other languages, reflecting the unique conceptual sphere of a nation.

Materials and Research Methods. The study is based on lexicographic data from contemporary explanatory dictionaries of English, French, and Russian, including the Cambridge Dictionary, the Larousse dictionary, as well as explanatory dictionaries by S. I. Ozhegov and D. N. Ushakov. Illustrative material was drawn from fiction, media sources, and ethnocultural

descriptions of holidays. The research employs methods such as sampling of lexical units, descriptive and semantic analysis of dictionary definitions, comparative analysis, and elements of cognitive-conceptual analysis aimed at identifying the ethnocultural specifics of the concept “holiday” in English, French, and Russian linguistic worldviews.

While the concept of “*holiday*” can be analyzed at the level of lexical meaning and cognitive structure, its full ethnocultural significance is revealed through concrete cultural practices. To illustrate how the semantic components of this concept are realized in linguistic and cultural contexts, it is relevant to examine representative holidays in English, French, and Russian traditions. Examining these holidays allows us to move beyond abstract definitions and see how the concept of “*holiday*” integrates religious, historical, social, and moral dimensions, expressed through symbols, rituals, phraseological units, and everyday language.

Results and Discussion. In the English linguistic worldview, the concept of “*holiday*” is primarily represented by the lexical units: *holiday*, *celebration*, and *festival*, each emphasizing different aspects of festive events.

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, *holiday* is defined as “an official day when you do not have to go to school or work.” The etymology of the word (*holy day*) highlights its historical connection with religious observances, while in modern usage it mainly emphasizes the idea of rest and exemption from everyday duties. For instance, the sentence “Christmas Day is a public holiday in the UK” demonstrates that *holiday* functions as an official day off recognized at the state level [3].

Another important lexical unit is *celebration*, which is defined as “an occasion when you celebrate a special day or event.” This definition shifts the focus from the formal status of a day to its emotional and event-based significance. In the example “Let’s buy some champagne in celebration of her safe arrival,” the

word *celebration* denotes a joyful event marking an important moment [3].

The dictionary also provides a second meaning of “celebration” — “the act of celebrating something,” which emphasizes the process of preparation and participation. Thus, in the sentence “Preparations were under way for his 80th birthday celebration in September,” *celebration* refers to the active organization and collective involvement in the festive process, highlighting its emotional and social dimensions [3].

The lexical unit *festival* complements this semantic field. Its first definition — “a special day or period when people celebrate something, especially a religious event” — stresses the connection with tradition, ritual, and a specific time frame. The second meaning — “a series of special events, performances, etc. that often takes place over several days” — expands the concept to include large-scale public events. For example, “The Edinburgh International Festival is a major celebration of music, theatre and dance, attracting visitors from all over the world” illustrates that *festival* may encompass cultural, artistic, and social activities extending beyond purely religious or personal celebrations [3].

To illustrate how these semantic components are realized in ethnocultural practice, it is relevant to consider one of the most significant English holidays — Christmas. Among such holidays as Halloween, Easter, Guy Fawkes Night, and St. George’s Day, Christmas occupies a special place, as it reflects both religious tradition and ethnocultural values of the English linguistic community. Christmas is a major Christian holiday celebrated in honor of the birth of Jesus Christ. Although the exact date of Christ’s birth is unknown, in the fourth century the Christian Church established December 25 as the day of celebration. This date coincided with ancient pagan winter solstice festivals, such as Saturnalia and Yule, symbolizing light, renewal, and new beginnings.

In England, Christmas is marked by various festive practices, including theatrical performances known as *Mysteries*, which depict biblical scenes related to the birth of Christ and reinforce the religious foundations of the holiday [4]. At the same time, Christmas functions as a public holiday (*holiday*), a joyful family event (*celebration*), and a culturally rich festive period (*festival*), thus integrating all the key semantic features identified in the dictionary analysis.

Christmas is also characterized by a rich system of symbols deeply rooted in tradition. The Christmas tree symbolizes eternal life and renewal; Santa Claus embodies kindness and generosity; the Christmas star represents the Star of Bethlehem and symbolizes spiritual guidance and hope. Carols create an atmosphere of unity and joy, while mistletoe symbolizes reconciliation, love, and peace. These symbols not only enhance the emotional intensity of the holiday but also reflect shared ethnocultural meanings.

An important role in the representation of Christmas is played by phraseological expressions that convey its cultural significance in everyday language. Expressions such as “Merry Christmas”, “Deck the halls”, and “Christmas came early” verbalize joy, anticipation, and festive preparation. The phrase “Good things come

in small packages” emphasizes emotional value over material wealth, while the idiom “The proof of the pudding is in the eating” highlights the idea that the true meaning of Christmas is revealed through lived experience, shared moments, and interpersonal warmth.

Thus, Christmas serves as a vivid example of how the English concept of “*holiday*” is realized in ethnocultural practice, combining official recognition, emotional celebration, collective participation, symbolism, and linguistic expression. It clearly demonstrates how dictionary meanings are embodied in traditions, rituals, and everyday speech, reflecting the values and worldview of English linguoculture.

Next, we will examine how the concept of “*holiday*” is represented in the French language.

In French, the concept of “*holiday*” is represented by the single word *fête*, which encompasses a range of social, religious, and personal celebrations. According to the Larousse dictionary, “*fête*” can denote a “*Solennité religieuse ou cérémonie commémorative*” (a religious celebration or commemorative ceremony), such as “*La messe de Noël est une fête solennelle pour les fidèles*” (The Christmas Mass is a solemn celebration for the faithful).

The second meaning is “*Jour consacré à la mémoire d'un saint considéré comme le patron d'un pays, d'un groupe, d'une profession ou dont une personne a reçu le nom comme prénom*” (a day dedicated to the memory of a saint considered the patron of a country, a group, a profession, or after whom a person has been named), reflecting the national-religious aspects of holidays honoring saints or patrons. For instance: “*La fête de la Saint-Patrick est célébrée en Irlande et dans le monde*” (Saint Patrick’s Day is celebrated in Ireland and around the world).

The third meaning is “*Réjouissances publiques destinées à commémorer périodiquement un fait mémorable, un événement, un héros, etc.*” (public festivities intended to periodically commemorate a memorable fact, an event, a hero, etc.), covering national or civic holidays. For example: “*Le 14 Juillet est une fête nationale en France*” (July 14th is a national holiday in France).

Finally, “*fête*” can also refer to “*Réjouissances, festin, bal offerts par quelqu'un en l'honneur de quelque chose*” (rejoicings, a feast, or a ball organized by someone in honor of something), highlighting family or personal celebrations. For example: “*Ils ont organisé une fête pour l'anniversaire de leur enfant*” (They organized a party for their child’s birthday) [6].

To illustrate how the semantic components of the concept “*fête*” are realized in French ethnocultural practice, it is relevant to consider one of the most representative and symbolically rich French holidays — **La Saint-Martin**. This holiday celebrated on 11 November. It marks the end of the agricultural year and the transition from autumn to winter, while also having Christian roots. It commemorates Saint Martin of Tours, a fourth-century Roman soldier who became a bishop and was renowned for his charitable act of sharing his cloak with a poor beggar [5, p. 8].

The central symbol of La Saint-Martin is *le manteau de Saint Martin* (Saint Martin's cloak), representing compassion, generosity, and solidarity. This symbolic image is reflected in the French phraseological unit "*partager son manteau*", meaning to help others selflessly or to share what one has with those in need. Another key element is "*la lumière*", symbolizing hope and inner warmth during the dark season, particularly visible in children's lantern processions, where light metaphorically conveys moral guidance and human kindness.

Linguistically, La Saint-Martin is associated with stable expressions that reflect folk beliefs and seasonal changes. For example, "*À la Saint-Martin, l'hiver est en chemin*" emphasizes this day as a turning point in the natural cycle, while "*être une lumière pour quelqu'un*", often linked to this holiday, conveys the idea of supporting and guiding others, aligning with Saint Martin's ethical message [7].

In contemporary French culture, La Saint-Martin is preserved mainly through regional traditions and educational practices, interpreted as a holiday of sharing and moral values. Thus, La Saint-Martin illustrates how the French concept of "*fête*" integrates religious meaning, symbolic imagery, and social ethics, reflecting important ethnocultural values of French society.

Having examined the concept of "*holiday*" in the English and French linguistic worldviews, we can now proceed to analyze its representation in the Russian language.

In the Russian linguistic worldview, the concept of "*holiday*" is represented by the lexical unit «*праздник*», which combines official, social, emotional, and collective meanings. According to Ozhegov's Explanatory Dictionary, «*праздник*» is defined as «*день торжества, установленный в честь чего-либо или в память кого-либо*» (a day of celebration established in honor of something or in memory of someone). This definition primarily refers to historical, religious, and social events that possess collective significance. For example, Metropolitan Anthony writes: «*Из года в год возвращается светлый, всерадостный праздник Рождества Христова*» (Year after year returns the bright, all-joyful holiday of Christmas), emphasizing the sacred and recurring nature of religious celebration in Russian culture [11].

The same dictionary also records a more modern interpretation of «*праздник*» as «*день массовых игр и развлечений*» (a day of mass games and entertainment), reflecting the transformation of the concept in contemporary society. This meaning is widely realized in educational and social contexts, where teachers organize events such as Health Day, Sports Day, or Alphabet Day. A representative example from the media illustrates this usage: «*Олимпиада была прекрасно организована, и хотя без недоразумений не обошлось, в целом великий праздник спорта, несомненно, удался*» (The Olympics were excellently organized, and although there were some misunderstandings, overall, the great sports festival was undoubtedly a success) [10]. In this case, «*праздник*» denotes a large-scale public event characterized by collective participation and emotional uplift.

Ushakov's dictionary further enriches the semantic structure of the concept by defining «*праздник*» as «*счастливый, радостный день, ознаменованный каким-нибудь важным, принятым событием, удачей и т.п.*» (a happy, joyful day marked by some important or successful event) [12]. This interpretation foregrounds the emotional and subjective dimension of the concept, highlighting personal and communal joy. An illustrative example can be found in Eduard Limonov's work *We Had a Great Era*: «*В один прекрасный осенний день по Свердлову пустили (это был праздник) трамвай!*» (On one fine autumn day, a tram was allowed to run along Sverdlova Street — it was a holiday!) [8]. Here, the word «*праздник*» metaphorically designates a socially meaningful event that brought joy to the residents, demonstrating the emotional and communal value of the concept.

A more complete understanding of the concept can be achieved through the analysis of its synonyms. One of them is «*торжество*», which denotes a solemn festivity held in honor of a significant event, for example: «*Торжество по случаю победы*» (Celebration on the occasion of a victory). This lexical unit emphasizes grandeur, importance, and elevated emotional tone. Another synonym is «*гулянье*», which refers to a public outdoor festivity and highlights the collective and social character of celebration. An example is «*Народные гулянья на Масленицу*» (Public festivities during Maslenitsa) [12]. These synonyms reveal the collective, emotional, and ritual nature of the Russian understanding of a holiday.

To illustrate how the semantic components of the concept «*праздник*» are realized in ethnocultural practice, it is relevant to consider one of the most ancient and symbolically rich Russian holidays — Maslenitsa. Alongside such important holidays as New Year, Easter, and Christmas, Maslenitsa occupies a special place in Russian linguoculture due to its deep historical roots and vivid ritual structure. Maslenitsa is celebrated during the last week before Great Lent and is associated with the transition from winter to spring. The name of the holiday originates from Orthodox tradition: during this week meat is excluded from the diet, while dairy products are still permitted, which explains the central role of pancakes.

The tradition of celebrating Maslenitsa dates back to ancient times and is connected with pagan Slavic rituals aimed at banishing winter and welcoming spring. Over time, these rituals merged with Christian practices, forming a complex ethnocultural phenomenon. Today, Maslenitsa is perceived as a holiday of farewell to winter and the anticipation of renewal [2, p. 3–4].

Maslenitsa is deeply embedded in the Russian linguoculture. Its symbolism and vocabulary reflect folk ideas about the cyclical nature of time, seasonal change, and communal unity. The primary symbol of the holiday is the *pancake*, which personifies the sun and the arrival of spring. This symbolism is reflected in commonly used expressions such as "bake pancakes" and "pancake day." Another key element is the *scarecrow*, symbolizing winter, which is traditionally burned at the end of the week, marking the transition to spring. The final day of Maslenitsa, known as *Forgiveness Sunday*,

emphasizes moral purification and reconciliation; typical expressions include “Forgive me” and “Forgiveness Sunday.”

Phraseological units associated with Maslenitsa further demonstrate the ethnocultural specificity of the concept. The expression “*First pancake’s a bust*” conveys the idea that initial attempts may be unsuccessful. “*Wide Maslenitsa*” symbolizes abundance, generosity, and the scale of festivities. The phrase “*On Maslenitsa the soul went wild*” reflects unrestricted joy and collective merriment, while “*Maslenitsa without pancakes is like a birthday party without pies*” emphasizes the inseparability of a holiday from its core symbolic attributes.

Thus, Maslenitsa serves as a vivid example of how the Russian concept of *праздник* is realized in ethnocultural practice, combining ritual, symbolism, collective celebration, and emotional expression. It demonstrates that in the Russian linguistic worldview a holiday is not merely an official date, but a socially and emotionally meaningful event deeply rooted in tradition and shared cultural memory.

Conclusion. The analysis of the concept of “*holiday*” across English, French, and Russian linguistic worldviews demonstrates that while the notion of a holiday is universal, its realization is deeply shaped by ethnocultural factors. In English, the concept emphasizes formal recognition, rest, and joy, as exemplified by Christmas, which integrates religious tradition, public celebration, and symbolic imagery. In French, the concept is represented by “*fête*”, encompassing religious, historical, social, and personal dimensions, with La Saint-Martin illustrating how ethical values, communal participation, and symbolic acts such as sharing a cloak are expressed through language and cultural practices. In Russian, the concept of “*праздник*” combines official, social, emotional, and collective meanings, with Maslenitsa exemplifying the integration of ancient rituals, seasonal symbolism, communal festivity, and moral dimensions.

Through the examination of these holidays, it becomes evident that the concept of “*holiday*” is not limited to a day of leisure or entertainment. Rather, it functions as a complex conceptual unit that reflects a community’s historical experience, ethical norms, seasonal perceptions, and collective identity. Rituals, symbols, phraseological units, and everyday language serve as carriers of these meanings, allowing members of a culture to transmit and preserve shared values across generations.

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